

Harmful Dinoflagellates in Odessa Bay (Black Sea)

Fig. 1. Map of sampling stations: Koblevo (Kb); Yuzhnoe (Yu); Luzanovka Lu; Od, Port (Od); Delphin (De); Chkalovskiy (Ch); Maliy Fontan (MF); Arcadia (Ar); Dacha Kovalevskogo (DK).

In the 1960s, anthropogenic eutrophication in the Black Sea greatly intensified, with an increased influx of biogenic elements leading to mass phytoplankton development [1]. By the early 1970s, the first cases of harmful algal blooms (HABs) caused by the dinoflagellate *Prorocentrum cordatum* (Ostenfeld) Dodge (= *P. minimum*; synonymy according to [2, 3]) were recorded in the northwestern part of the sea [4]. Currently, *P. cordatum* remains one of the most abundant species of harmful dinoflagellates in Odessa Bay and the Black Sea, in general [5, 6].

By the 2000s, HAB episodes in the bay were induced by other dinoflagellates: *Akashiwo sanguinea* (Hirasaka) Hansen & Moestrup, *Protodinium simplex* Lohmann, *Gyrodinium cornutum* (Pouchet) Kofoid & Swezy, *Levanderina fissa* (Levander) Moestrup, Hakanen, Gert Hansen, Daugbjerg & M.Ellegaard 2014, *Lingulaulax polyedra* (F.Stein) M.J.Head, K.N.Mertens & R.A.Fensome 2024, *Kryptoperidinium triquetrum* (Ehrenberg) Tillmann, Gottschling, Elbrächter, Kusber & Hoppenrath 2019 (Ehrenberg) Stein, *Scrippsiella trochoidea* (Stein) Loeblich, and *Prorocentrum micans* Ehrenberg [7].

In this study, harmful algal species Dinoflagellata of Odessa Bay were sampled monthly between 2020 and 2024 at eight stations located in the coastal zone (Fig. 1). Salinity at the sampling sites ranged from 12 to 17. In summer 2023, salinity values as low as 3.9 were recorded following the destruction of the Kakhovka Reservoir during military actions. A very intense cyanobacterial bloom developed during the most acute phase of the impact, lasting about three months [8].

Phytoplankton samples were examined with Mikmed-2 and Olympus BX51 light microscopes equipped with differential interference contrast (DIC, Nomarski), and epifluorescence, with preliminary staining of the cells with Calcofluor White M2R [9]. Some samples were also examined using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) JEOL JSM-35C and a field emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM) JEOL JAMP 9500F, following the protocol specified by [10].

The analyses of samples revealed the presence of 18 harmful species [11] in Odessa Bay associated with the following syndromes:

1. Shellfish toxin producers:
 - Paralytic shellfish poisoning (PSP): *Alexandrium minutum* Halim.
 - DSP and PTX: *Dinophysis acuminata* Claparède & Lachmann, *D. acuta* Ehrenberg, *D. caudata* Kent, *D. fortii* Pavillard, *D. hastata* Stein, *D. ovum* Schütt, *D. sacculus* Stein, *Phalacroma rotundatum* (Claparède & Lachmann) Kofoid & J.R.Michener 1911 and benthic *P. lima* (Ehrenberg) Stein.
 - Yessotoxins YTX: *Gonyaulax spinifera* (Claparède & Lachmann) Bütschli, *Lingulaulax polyedra* (F.Stein) M.J.Head, K.N.Mertens & R.A.Fensome 2024 and *Protocera-tium reticulatum* (Claparède & Lachmann) Bütschli (Fig. 2).
2. Fish and invertebrate mass mortalities: *Margalefidinium polykrikoides* (Margalef) Gómez, Richlen & Anderson: High biomass HABs.
3. Anoxic events: *Akashiwo sanguinea* (Hirasaka) Hansen & Moestrup.
4. Mucilage and other physical-mechanical problems: *Kryptoperidinium triquetrum* (Ehrenberg) Tillmann, Gottschling, Elbrächter, Kusber & Hoppenrath 2019 (Ehrenberg) Stein; *Prorocentrum cordatum* (Ostenfeld) Dodge.

Currently, *Lingulaulax polyedra* has become the dominant HAB species in terms of abundance in Odessa Bay. In 2020 and 2024, this dinoflagellate caused water discolorations near Odessa seaport. On October 6, 2020, a cell maximum of 56.1×10^6 cells·L⁻¹ was recorded at a temperature 19.7°C and salinity 14.3 [12]. In late September, 2024, the cell maximum was 11.5×10^6 cells·L⁻¹, under very similar conditions of temperature (19.7–20.0°C) and salinity (13.9–15.9) as in the 2020 bloom.

Such high cell densities have been associated with high nutrient levels in this area of Odessa Bay. Outbreaks of *L. polyedra* occurred following heavy rains and runoff from adjacent territories. Different abiotic and biotic drivers have been suggested as potential causes of *L. polyedra* red tides. These include observed trends of increasing air and sea-water temperatures, the resuspension of *L. polyedra* cysts from the seabed to the surface layers of the sea and strong wind-driven advection of offshore populations of *L. polyedra*, leading to high

Fig. 2. Light microscopy and scanning electron micrographs of potentially toxic and harmful dinoflagellates of Odessa Bay: (A). *Akashiwo sanguinea*. (B). *Alexandrium minutum*. (C). *Dinophysis acuminata*. (D). *D. acuta*. (E). *D. caudata*. (F). *D. fortii*. (G–H). *D. sacculus*. (I). *D. hastata*. (J). *D. ovum*. (K). *Phalacroma rotundatum*. (L, P, T). *Protoceratium reticulatum*. (M). *Gonyaulax spinifera*. (N). *Kryptoperidinium triquetra*. (O). *Prorocentrum lima*. (Q). *P. cordatum*. (R). *Lingulaulax polyedra*. (S). *Durinskia baltica*. Original photos. Images not to scale.

cell numbers in the surface layer of Odessa Bay. During the discolorations, an intense glow of the seawater was observed in the evening and at night.

In conclusion, the ongoing monitoring and understanding of harmful dinoflagellate species in Odessa Bay are crucial for managing the ecological impacts of nutrient enrichment, climate change, and human activities, ensuring the protection of marine biodiversity and the health of local ecosystems.

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